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PROGRAM - TARGET PROJECT AS THE MOST IMPORTANT ASPECT OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

Oksana Polishchuk. *«Program-target project as the most important aspect of public administration».* The article is devoted to the analysis of the possibilities of developing targeted programs and projects. The interrelation of the program-target management method with other management methods and its implementation at the regional level has been analyzed. When preparing targeted programs and projects, methodological errors are often made. In particular, the goal of solving the problem and the requirements for achieving it are not specifically formulated. This significantly complicates the assessment of the compliance of existing projects and program objectives, and also interferes with an objective perception of the current state of the solution to the problem. It is for this purpose that recommendations for further research have been provided.

Keywords: target programs, globalization, project, management method, strategic planning.

Оксана Поліщук *«Програмно-цільовий проект як найважливіший аспект державного управління».* Стаття присвячена аналізу можливостей розробки цільових програм та проектів. Проаналізовано взаємозв'язок програмно-цільового методу управління з іншими методами управління та його реалізацію на регіональному рівні. Під час підготовки цільових програм і проектів нерідко допускаються методичні похибки. Зокрема, недостатньо конкретно формулюється мета вирішення проблеми та вимоги до її досягнення. Це ускладнює оцінку відповідності наявних проектів та завдань програми, а також заважає об'єктивному сприйняттю поточного стану вирішення проблеми. Саме з цією метою надано рекомендації щодо подальших досліджень.

Ключові слова: цільові програми, глобалізація, проект, метод керування, стратегічне планування.

Оксана Полищук *«Програмно-целевой проект как важнейший аспект государственного управления».* Статья посвящена анализу возможностей разработки целевых программ и проектов. Проанализировано взаимосвязь программно-целевого метода управления с другими методами управления и его реализация на региональном уровне. При подготовке целевых программ и проектов нередко допускаются методические погрешности. В частности, недостаточно конкретно формулируется цель решения проблемы и требования к ее достижению. Это существенно затрудняет оценку соответствия имеющихся проектов и задач программы, а также мешает объективному восприятию текущего состояния решения проблемы. Именно с этой целью предоставлено рекомендации дальнейших исследований.

Ключевые слова: целевые программы, глобализация, проект, метод управления, стратегическое планирование.

Introduction. The globalization of economic activity is one of the main issues in

the development of the modern world, since it affects not only the economic life of the

country, but also entails political (domestic and international), as well as social consequences. A modern instrument of state influence on the processes of socio-economic development is the use of a program-targeted method of management. This method is a set of tactically interrelated measures of a technical, economic, social and organizational nature, aimed at achieving a specific goal in the development of the state. For program-targeted management at various regional levels, information on the further development of the region is of great importance, allowing, when making a decision, to comprehensively take into account long-term consequences, so that they do not contradict the interests of other regions and the state as a whole. Such participation, in turn, should be manifested in the formation of such a state policy that contributes to the equalization of the levels of socio-economic development of regions, their economic growth.

The main tasks of the analysis should be aimed at identifying the achieved level, disclosing the most important trends in the development of the economic complex, social sphere, reforming economic relations, social status of the population and the ecological situation, determining both individual shortcomings (imbalances) and positive phenomena, identifying reserves development and socio-economic potential.

Analysis of recent research and publications. A notable scientific contribution to this area of research was made by such famous scientists - economists as: G. Kerol, G. Atamanchuk, V. Abalkin, A. Granberg, V. Davidenko, N. Larina, N. Leksin, V. Tsvetkov, M. Fedorenko and others, whose works are devoted to the problems of development, program-target management. The improvement of the territorial organization of society is attracting more and more attention of practically all political forces of state authorities, public organizations, academic economists and businessmen. A significant revival of public interest in this issue is due to the

understanding that there cannot be a single approach to the concept of economy in every geographically diversified state, each region is distinguished by its historical, economic, ecological, geographic and demographic characteristics and has its own ethnic and cultural traditions. The issues of target-oriented management have not yet been fully investigated, therefore there is a need to pay attention to the issues of developing programs for a different target approach to economic directions.

The purpose and objectives of the study. The use of targeted programs in the practice of managing socio-economic development is caused by the need to preserve both external market relations (tariff agreements, mechanisms for correcting the tax system in the interests of market stability, etc.) and internal processes of state (regional) management.

The main incentive for the development of a program is due to the possibility of obtaining budgetary funds or guarantees from the bank and funds that lend to programs on terms of return. The programs that are submitted both at the regional and municipal levels are quite specific and focused on solving current problems. At the same time, there are also programs-directions of a regional or intersectoral nature, the scale and resource requirements of which significantly exceed the real possibilities of the investment potential. In addition, in the preparation of target programs, methodological errors are often made. In particular, the goal of solving the problem and the requirements for achieving it are not specifically formulated. This significantly complicates the assessment of the compliance of existing projects and program objectives, and also interferes with an objective perception of the current state of the solution to the problem.

The composition of the final sub-goals and projects included in the program do not always take into account the market situation and often do not correspond to the goal of solving the problem as a whole. Taking into

account the peculiarities of using program-targeted management in the process of solving problems of socio-economic development at the regional and municipal levels, it can be noted that its potential capabilities are realized only with an adequate assessment of a specific situation, with the correct implementation of the principles of the program-oriented approach.

This is of fundamental importance, since it is necessary to observe specific forms, methods and procedures of management. In turn, this is due to integration and corporate processes, an increase in the size of individual programs, and an increase in complexity. Increasingly, large programs go beyond the boundaries of one department, and, therefore, require coordinated activities and implementation at the interdepartmental level. In general, this does not contradict the rather broad concept of the target program, which is defined as a mutually agreed project on the use of resources, performers, and the deadlines for the implementation of a complex of research, design, production, socio-economic, economic and other tasks that provide an effective solution are open regulation in the state.

A more detailed approach includes the rationale for choosing a specific problem for software development and is characterized by the following points:

- formulation of the problem and analysis of the causes of its occurrence;

- assessment of the need for financial, budgetary and extra-budgetary, material and labor resources, and determination of possible sources of their provision; determination of the range of possible government bodies (customers), and developers (executors) of the program.

Generalization of theoretical conclusions and specific experience of researchers of this issue allows us to single out the following, more appropriate for the development of targeted programs, principles [1]:

- orientation of the program to the final result (formulated in the form of goals or a set

- of goals), the achievement of which becomes the main purpose of the program;

- building a program in the form of a group (complex) of ordered, interconnected activities of different levels that form its structure;

- definition of small elements of the program; understanding of the program as an integral control object, regardless of the belonging of its constituent elements; systematic consideration of the management process at all stages - from analyzing the problem and setting goals to monitoring the implementation of the program;

- creation of an appropriate organizational program management system either on the basis of a specially introduced body, or by redistributing the rights and responsibilities of existing units, as well as the use of different coordination forms of management.

The actualization of the use of the program-target form in management is facilitated by a new, market-oriented economic management mechanism. The tendency to improve the methods and forms of organization of management is to increase the independence of the primary level of management, as well as expand the competence of territorial regulation in the production and sale of goods and services. To organize an effective solution to socio-economic problems by methods of program-target planning and management, it is necessary to form bodies of program-target orientation, carry out problem-oriented assessments, information support of management. So in a democratic, legal, social society, the main place belongs to the interaction of various types of social mechanisms with the use of democratic social technologies (elections, negotiations, referendums, public opinion studies), the implementation of the principles of social partnership and joint responsibility.

At the same time, the main requirement is that social management should be focused on a person, on his all-round development. In modern dictionaries, this is described as the activities of the state and other political, social

institutions aimed at the progressive development of the social sphere of society, improving the conditions, lifestyle and quality of life of people, ensuring a certain part of their vital needs, providing citizens with social support, assistance and protection.

In the aggregate of subjects of social policy, the state plays a key role. Some scholars define social policy as a function of state responsibility for the use of public resources.

An important technology of modern social policy is, firstly, social forecasting. Social forecasts are carried out in at least two ways - through the search for possible states, determining certain tendencies and extrapolating the situation, and through the normative path - determining alternative or optimal possibilities and timing of achieving the desired state, i.e. ways of solving problems based on the specified optimum criteria.

The next technology is social design as a process of creating prototypes of social phenomena and processes, in the course of such design, both internal and external social resources are identified that can be activated to solve social problems.

Another technology is social planning - it is a scientifically grounded definition of goals, indicators, tasks, deadlines, rates, proportions of the development of social processes and the main means of their implementation. The objects of social planning are society as a whole, each of the spheres of social life, social processes that take place in various spheres of society, both territorially and functionally (in the service sector, etc.).

Tactical measures play an important role in the implementation of the strategy of socio-economic development, its implementation. In this case, tactics act as a tool that contributes to a long-term strategy. The lack of a clear delineation of powers between central and local bodies of executive power and self-government on the management of the socio-economic development of regions indicates that the state needs the development of the economy and legal framework. It should be noted that

over the years of the country's economic development, planning, being the main method of the rational and economic process, acquired new qualities, improved, reflecting the specific tasks of further development. That is why many scientists now defend positions on the continued use of planning (indicative, strategic, structural, programmatic) in the system of state regulation of the economy.

In modern economic science, there are two main approaches to the principles of state regulation and management of the economy of the country and its regions. On the one hand, this is the desire to improve the planned management mechanisms, on the other, it is the introduction of new, programmatic methods of regulation. The presence of shortcomings of market self-regulation and shortcomings of government intervention in the economy gives rise to complex socio-economic problems, the solution of which is associated with the use of the so-called program-targeted method of planning.

The use of the target-oriented planning method provides for:

- problem definition and formulation of goals;
- development and implementation of a program aimed at achieving goals;
- systematic control over the quality and results of the work stipulated by the program;
- adjustments of measures aimed at achieving the goals.

The application of the target-oriented approach is due to many factors:

- availability of demand for products (work, transportation services);
- excessive waste of resources and, as a consequence, the emergence of negative external effects;
- the need for deep structural transformations.

The target-oriented planning method is implemented through target programs. Target Comprehensive Program (PCP) is a document that contains the timing, funding, personnel to ensure the goals of the project.

The goals to which the CCU should be directed are noted in the strategy of the state's socio-economic policy. The classification of the CCU is carried out according to the following main features: by level, composition, sphere of influence and implementation, by the nature and specifics of tasks and goals, by deadlines.

According to the level, composition, spheres of influence and implementation, the following programs are distinguished: interstate, state, intersectoral, sectoral, interregional, regional, local.

By the nature and specifics of problems and goals, programs are distinguished: socio-economic, aimed at solving development problems and improving the way of life, increasing the material and cultural level of the population, improving industrial and social conditions of work and rest, etc.

Production, focused on increasing the production of certain types of products (work, services), the development of progressive industries, improving the quality characteristics of products, increasing the efficiency of resource use.

Scientific and technical, aimed at the development of scientific research, solving problems of the development and implementation of new equipment and technology in practice.

Environmental, aimed at resource conservation, the implementation of environmental projects.

Institutional, focused on improving the organization of management in the system of transformation of property relations.

Regional, aimed at the economic development of new areas.

According to the terms of implementation, the programs are divided into the following types: long-term (designed for a period of 5-10 years); medium-term (1-5 years); and short-term (up to 1 year). This classification is due to the nature of the goals that the program aims to achieve. Long-term programs are aimed at achieving strategic goals. As a rule, achieving a strategic goal is a long-term process that is associated with

different levels of economic development and cannot be carried out quickly. Medium-term programs unleash tactical challenges. Short-term programs are aimed at solving current problems (operational goals).

Programming as a way to solve economic problems is used in various parts of the organizational structure of the economy. The most important programs aimed at solving national and social problems, which are formed based on the strategic goals of the state, acquire the status of national programs. The development and implementation of the CKP requires the performance of a certain set of works (tasks) related to technical and economic planning, production, financing, etc. The set of tasks stipulated by the program can be grouped into two blocks: the main activity and its support.

The main activities include: pre-investment planning research, development of design and estimate documentation, conclusion of contracts, overhaul, construction and installation work, commissioning of facilities, etc.

Support activities include organizational, legal, personnel, financial, material and technical, marketing, information support. Each ICU, regardless of its amount of funding and work, is in various states: from the state when the program is not yet available to the state when the program is no longer there. The period of time from the moment the program was created until the moment of its liquidation is called the life cycle of the ICU. According to current practice, the state through which the ICT passes are called stages (phases, stages). In turn, each stage can be subdivided into sub-stages, sub-phases, etc.

According to the systematic approach and the basic principles of program-oriented planning (target orientation towards achieving final results, complexity, alternativeness, controllability), the MSC is carried out according to the following scheme:

1. Selection of the list of problems to be solved programmatically.

2. Formation and issuance of the initial problem for the development of the program.
3. Development of the draft program.
4. Program approval.
5. Implementation of the program.
6. Report on the implementation of the program.

As for the existing methods for determining the costs of the formation and implementation of targeted programs, they can be conditionally divided into two groups depending on whether the developed version has an analogue in the past, or the development has a fundamentally new character.

If the developed version has an analogue, the amount of expenses for using the target regional program has the property of

adaptability, and can be calculated as the sum of expenses for the implementation of software projects [3]:

$$NC = \sum_{i=1}^N C(i) = 1$$

where: C- is the cost of implementing the i-th software project, CKP.;

N - is the number of projects in the program.

The implementation of individual tasks, which are integral parts of a software project, is determined by the current standards by analogy with previously performed work. The implementation of software projects is determined based on the following formulas:

$$n m T_i = \sum_{j=1}^m T_{ji} - \sum_{l=1}^n t_l (Pl_i - 1)$$

where:

T_i - implementation time of the j-th software project;

T_{ji} - implementation of the j-th task included in the software project (and is determined by the current standards and analogy with previously performed robots);

t_l - the duration of the l-th time interval during which several tasks included in the i-th software project are implemented in parallel;

Pl_i - the number of tasks implemented in parallel and included in programs on the l-th time interval;

n - the number of tasks included in the software project;

m - the number of time intervals in which the parallel implementation of tasks included in software design is carried out.

The total duration of the program is determined based on the expression:

$$N L T = \sum_{i=1}^N T_i - \sum_{r=1}^L tr(r-1)(3)$$

where:

T_i - is the implementation time of the i-th software project;

tr - is the duration of the r-th time interval during which several software projects are being implemented in parallel;

rt - is the number of software projects on the r-th time interval, implemented in parallel;

N - is the number of projects in the program;

L - is the number of time intervals on which the parallel implementation of projects included in the program is carried out.

It should be noted that when calculating the time for the implementation of the program, there are three possible approaches to determining the priority of the implementation of software projects:

sequential - projects (tasks) that are included in the program are included in the work after the completion of the previous program income;

parallel - projects included in the program are executed simultaneously;

mixed - along with the sequential inclusion in the work of projects (tasks) that are included in the program, the possibility of parallel implementation of some of them is provided.

When designing and developing fundamentally new, original options for the implementation of program projects that have no analogues in the past, as well as in the case of insufficient statistical information for the application of calculation methods, the amount of expenses for the implementation of software projects and the time of their implementation are determined by the examination method.

Thus, when choosing a program and method for implementing a program-targeted project in the socio-economic sphere, one must proceed from:

a) the special importance of targeted programs for the implementation of major structural changes and increasing the efficiency of regional development;

b) the short time frame for solving priority problems and the need to concentrate resources;

c) the relationship of the relevant projects (tasks).

Conclusions. The use of program-targeted methods in territorial planning and management increases the efficiency of state influence on the socio-economic development of regions, ensures the relationship between the allocated budget resources and the results of their use in accordance with the established priorities

and should be accompanied by increased monitoring and control over the implementation of targeted programs in the region. and priority projects as the main tools for target program planning.

The procedure and methodology for the development and implementation of programs and development plans differ depending on their level and scope of action, factors of selection of problems for program-targeted solutions: the significance of the problem; the complexity of solving problems within an acceptable time frame due to the use of the existing market mechanism and state support for its solution; fundamental novelty and high efficiency of technical, organizational and other measures necessary for the large-scale dissemination of progressive scientific and technological achievements and on this basis increase the efficiency of social production; the need to coordinate the actions of technologically related industries and industries to solve the problem.

The role of program-targeted methods, targeted programs in the management of the national and regional economy will grow steadily. The processes of world economic integration, globalization, involving different countries, regions, organizations, social groups in their orbit, can be coordinated and ordered only on the basis of the application of the program methodology. The relevance of this work will increase every day. The prospect of researching a program-targeted project in the socio-economic sphere is very timely, therefore, these issues should be dealt with more actively in the future.

References

1. Demin G. A. Methods for making managerial decisions [Electronic resource] URL: <http://www.psu.ru/files/docs/science/books/uchebnie-posobiya/demin-metody-prinyatiya-upravlencheskikh-reshenij.pdf>.

2. Closing the loop – An EU action plan for the circular economy <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52015DC0614&from=ES>

2019, December 2-4, 2019, Zakopane, Poland, 339-346.

3. Pearce, D., Markandya, A., Barbier, E. (1989). *Blueprint for a Green economy*. London: Earthscan Publications Ltd.
4. UNEP (2011). *Towards a Green Economy: Pathways to Sustainable Development and Poverty Eradication – A Synthesis for Policy Makers*. https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/126GER_synthesis_en.pdf.
5. Zaloznova, Yu., Kwilinski, A., Trushkina, N. (2018). Reverse logistics in a system of the circular economy: theoretical aspect. *Economic Herald of the Donbas*, 4(54), 29-37.
6. Trushkina, N. (2018). Green logistics as a tool to improve the quality of life in conditions of globalization. *Contemporary Problems of Improve Living Standards in a Globalized World: Volume of Scientific Papers* (pp. 147-152). Opole, Publishing House WSZiA.
7. Hryhorak, M. Yu., Trushkina, N. V. (2020). Development of the logistics system of the economic region "Polissya" in the context of the green economy: ecological problems and perspectives". *Intellectualization of logistics and Supply Chain Management*, 4, 27-40. <https://doi.org/10.46783/smart-scm/2020-4-3>.
8. European Commission (2018). *Impacts of Circular Economy Policies on the Labour Market. Final Report and Annexes*. Luxembourg.
9. Kojvisto, T. (2020). The Finnish Five: Circular Economy (interview with Kari Herlevi). September 25. <https://www.goodnewsfinland.com/ru/feature/finskaya-pyaterka-tsirkulyarnaya-ekonomika/>.